

Prevalence of Bacterial Isolates and Their Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern in Suspected Neonatal Septicemia: A Cross-Sectional Study in Jaipur, India

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Abstract

Background: Neonatal septicemia is a significant contributor to neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations. Identification of causative pathogens and understanding their antimicrobial resistance profiles are critical for timely and effective treatment.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted from January to March 2025 in the NICU of NIMS Hospital, Jaipur. Blood cultures from 32 neonates suspected of septicemia were processed using the BACTEC FX system. Isolates were identified and subjected to antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) using the VITEK 2 COMPACT system according to CLSI guidelines.

Results: Of the 32 neonates, 8 (25%) were culture-positive. Gram-negative bacilli constituted 87.5% of isolates, with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (37.5%) being the most common, followed by *Pseudomonas spp.* (25%), *E. coli*, *Acinetobacter spp.*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (each 12.5%). High resistance was observed to amoxicillin-

clavulanic acid, third-generation cephalosporins, and carbapenems. Tigecycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole showed 100% sensitivity.

Conclusion: Multidrug-resistant gram-negative organisms dominate neonatal septicemia in the NICU setting. There is an urgent need for regular surveillance, judicious antibiotic use, and stringent infection control policies.

Keywords: Neonatal sepsis, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, antimicrobial resistance, MDR

Introduction

Neonatal septicemia, an invasive bacterial infection occurring in infants within the first 28 days of life, remains a significant global health concern. It continues to be a primary cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing and low-income countries where access to timely healthcare and infection control practices may be limited. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), neonatal sepsis accounts for a considerable proportion of neonatal deaths worldwide, with approximately 3 million newborns dying each year from infections, of which sepsis is a leading cause .[1]

In India, neonatal sepsis remains a prominent public health issue, contributing to nearly 30% to 50% of all neonatal deaths.[2] The high burden can be attributed to several factors including limited access to quality healthcare facilities, lack of awareness, unskilled birth attendance, poor hygienic conditions, and inadequate infection control measures in healthcare settings. The situation is further exacerbated by the increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens that complicate the treatment regimen.

Neonatal sepsis is broadly categorized into two forms: Early-Onset Sepsis (EOS) and Late-Onset Sepsis (LOS). EOS typically manifests within the first 72 hours of life and is commonly caused by pathogens acquired from the maternal genital tract. Transmission may occur in utero or during passage through the birth canal. Common risk factors for EOS include prolonged rupture of membranes, maternal fever, urinary tract infections, and premature birth. On the other hand, LOS usually occurs after 72 hours of life and is frequently acquired from the hospital environment (nosocomial) or

community. LOS is associated with factors such as prolonged hospital stay, invasive procedures, mechanical ventilation, and indwelling catheters.[3]

The clinical manifestations of neonatal sepsis are often non-specific and may include temperature instability, poor feeding, irritability, lethargy, respiratory distress, cyanosis, and jaundice. Because these symptoms are shared with several other neonatal conditions, laboratory investigations are crucial for establishing a definitive diagnosis. Blood culture remains the gold standard for diagnosis, although it has limitations such as low yield and delayed results. Therefore, adjunctive biomarkers like C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin, and complete blood count (CBC) parameters are routinely employed to support early diagnosis and guide treatment.

The emergence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) among pathogens responsible for neonatal sepsis poses a critical threat to global health. The indiscriminate and empirical use of broad-spectrum antibiotics has led to the evolution of drug-resistant organisms. In particular, Gram-negative bacilli such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter spp.* have demonstrated high resistance to commonly used antibiotics including third-generation cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, and even carbapenems. This resistance trend significantly narrows down the choice of effective antimicrobial agents and leads to treatment failure, prolonged hospitalization, increased healthcare costs, and higher mortality rates.

Several Indian studies have highlighted the shifting bacterial spectrum in neonatal septicemia. Earlier dominated by Gram-positive organisms like Group B Streptococcus (GBS), the trend has shifted in favor of Gram-negative bacilli, particularly in hospital settings. Recent reports indicate *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as the most common cause of neonatal sepsis in tertiary care hospitals across India. Furthermore, the prevalence of Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) and Carbapenem-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) among these isolates is alarmingly high.[4]

The choice of empirical therapy in neonatal sepsis is primarily guided by the knowledge of local pathogen distribution and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns. Standard empirical regimens may include combinations of ampicillin with gentamicin or third-generation cephalosporins. However, due to the rising AMR, these regimens often require modification based on institutional antibiograms and regular surveillance data.[6]

The importance of antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASP) in neonatal units cannot be overemphasized. These programs involve implementing evidence-based guidelines for the judicious use of antibiotics, monitoring antibiotic consumption, conducting periodic audits, and training healthcare professionals. ASPs have been shown to reduce inappropriate antibiotic usage and improve clinical outcomes in NICUs.[9]

In addition to antimicrobial therapy, supportive care including adequate nutrition, maintenance of thermoregulation, oxygen therapy, and monitoring for complications is essential. Infection prevention strategies such as hand hygiene, aseptic techniques, breastfeeding promotion, and minimizing unnecessary invasive procedures are also vital components of neonatal care.

In the context of Jaipur and the broader Rajasthan region, there is a paucity of updated data regarding the current bacteriological profile and resistance patterns in neonatal septicemia. The present study was undertaken to bridge this knowledge gap and provide valuable insights for clinicians and microbiologists. By identifying the prevalent bacterial pathogens and evaluating their antibiotic sensitivity patterns, this study aims to enhance the effectiveness of empirical therapy and reduce the burden of neonatal sepsis in hospital settings.

Materials and Methods

This prospective cross-sectional study was conducted at the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, from January 1 to March 31, 2025. A total of 32 neonates presenting with clinical signs and symptoms suggestive of septicemia were included in the study. Inclusion criteria comprised neonates admitted to NICU exhibiting symptoms such as temperature instability, lethargy, respiratory distress, poor feeding, or irritability.

Blood samples were collected under strict aseptic conditions and inoculated into BACTEC culture bottles. The samples were incubated in the BACTEC FX system, which detects microbial growth based on CO₂ production. Positive blood cultures were subcultured on Blood agar and MacConkey agar for further isolation. The bacterial isolates were identified using standard microbiological techniques, including biochemical tests, and were further confirmed using the VITEK 2 COMPACT automated identification system.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of the isolates was performed using the VITEK 2 system, following the guidelines established by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). The panel of antibiotics tested included amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, meropenem, tigecycline, amikacin, and other clinically relevant antimicrobial agents.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

Among the 32 neonates, 21 (65.6%) were male and 11 (34.4%) were female. Culture positivity was observed in 8 (25%) cases.

TABLE.1 GENDER DISTRIBUTION

GENDER DISTRIBUTION				
GENDER	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENT (%)	CUMULATIVE PERCENT (%)	MEAN (\pm Std. Deviation)
MALE	21	65.6	65.6	1.34 (\pm 0.483)
FEMALE	11	34.4	100	
TOTAL	32	100		

GRAPH. 1 Gender Distribution (%)**Distribution of Isolates**

Out of 8 positive cultures:

Among the organisms isolated from blood culture samples, ***Klebsiella pneumoniae* spp. pneumoniae** was the most frequently identified pathogen, accounting for **37.5%** (n=3) of the total isolates.

***Pseudomonas* species** were the second most common, with **25%** (n=2) of the isolates.

E. coli*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Staphylococcus aureus were each isolated once, comprising **12.5%** (n=1) of the total respectively.

Overall, **Gram-negative organisms** constituted the majority of isolates (**87.5%**, 7 out of 8), while **Gram-positive organisms** made up **12.5%** (1 out of 8).

TABLE NO:DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISMS ISOLATED FROM BLOOD CULTURE (n = 8)

DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISMS ISOLATED FROM BLOOD CULTURE (n = 8)		
ORGANISMS	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENT (%)
Klebsiella Pneumoniae	3	37.5
Pseudomonas	2	25
Escherichia -Coli	1	12.5
Acinetobacter	1	12.5
Staphylococcus aureus	1	12.5
TOTAL	8	100.0

- ✧ *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: 3 (37.5%)
- ✧ *Pseudomonas spp.*: 2 (25%)
- ✧ *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter spp.*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*: 1 each (12.5%)

Gram-negative bacilli accounted for 87.5% of the isolates.

Antibiotic Resistance Patterns

All gram-negative organisms exhibited high resistance to:

- ✧ Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (100%)
- ✧ Ceftriaxone (100%)
- ✧ Imipenem (100%)

Tigecycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole showed 100% sensitivity across all isolates. Amikacin demonstrated sensitivity in 85.7% of cases.

The single *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate was resistant to vancomycin and teicoplanin but was sensitive to linezolid.

Gram-Negative Organisms – Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile				
Antibiotic	Pseudomonas(2)	E. Coli (1)	Acinetobacter (1)	Klebsiella Pneumoniae (3)
Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid	R (2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Piperacillin/Tazobactam	R (2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Cefuroxime	R (2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Cefuroxime Axetil	R (2/2)	R	R	I (3/3)
Ceftriaxone	R(2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Cefepime	R(2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Cefoperazone/sulbactam	R(2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Ertapenem	R(2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Imipenem	R (2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Meropenem	I (2/2)	R	I	S (3/3)
Gentamicin	I (1/2) /S(1/2)	I	I	S (1/3) R (2/3)
Amikacin	S (2/2)	S	I	S (3/3)
Ciprofloxacin	R(2/2)	R	R	R (3/3)
Tigecyclin	S(2/2)	S	S	S (3/3)
Colistn	S(2/2)	S	R	I (1/3) S (2/3)

Polymyxin B	R(2/2)	R	R	S (/3)
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	S(2/2)	S	S	S (3/3)
Ofloxacin	R(2/2)	R	R	I (3/3)
Chloramphenicol	R(2/2)	R	R	S (3/3)

Sensitivity and resistance pattern among isolated gram negative organisms :

Antibiotic	Sensitive	Intermediate semnsitive	Resistant
Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid	0	0	7 (100%)
Piperacillin/Tazobactam	0	0	7 (100%)
Cefuroxime	0	0	7 (100%)
Cefuroxime Axetil	0	3(42.6%)	4(57.14%)
Ceftriaxone	0	0	7 (100%)
Cefepime	0	0	7 (100%)
Cefoperazone/sulbactam	0	0	7 (100%)
Ertapenem	0	0	7 (100%)
Imipenem	0	0	7 (100%)
Meropenem	3(42.86%)	3(42.86%)	1(14.29%)
Gentamicin	2(28.57%)	3(42.86%)	2(28.57%)
Amikacin	6(85.71)	1(14.29%)	0
Ciprofloxacin	0	0	7 (100%)
Tigecycline	7 (100%)	0	0
Colistn	5(71.43%)	1(14.29%)	1(14.29%)

Polymyxin B	3(42.86%)	0	4(57.14%)
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	7(100%)	0	0
Ofloxacin	0	3(42.86%)	4(57.14%)
Chloramphenicol	3(42.86%)	0	4(57.14%)

Interpretation:

Gram-negative organisms show extensive resistance to β -lactams and carbapenems, including Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid, Piperacillin/Tazobactam, Cefepime, and Imipenem.

Tigecycline and Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole were the only antibiotics with consistent sensitivity across all species.

Meropenem Amikacin and Gentamicin show variable results. Resistance to last-resort drugs like Colistin and Polymyxin B is also noted, indicating a concerning multidrug-resistant pattern.

Similarly in gram positive bacteria sensitivity for multiple antibiotics was seen and results are as follows :

Gram-Positive Organisms – Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile	
Antibiotic	Staph aureus
Benzylopenicillin	R
Levofloxacin	R
Erythromycin	R
Linezolid	S
Teicoplanin	R
Vancomycin	R
Nitrofurantoin	R
Ciprofloxacin	I
Gentamicin	I
Tigecycline	I

Statistical Findings

A statistically significant association was observed between organism type and sensitivity pattern ($p = 0.043$), while resistance patterns did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

This study confirms the predominance of gram-negative bacilli, particularly *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, in neonatal septicemia, a finding that is consistent with other regional and national reports such as those by Kumar et al. (2024) and Chauhan et al. (2023).[4,5] The frequent isolation of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* underscores its role as a leading cause of both early-onset and late-onset neonatal infections, especially in settings with high rates of hospitalization, preterm births, and invasive interventions. In our study, this pathogen demonstrated extensive resistance to a wide range of beta-lactam antibiotics, including cephalosporins and carbapenems, reflecting a broader global pattern of escalating resistance among Enterobacteriaceae (Sharma et al., 2022).[6]

The emergence and persistence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) organisms in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) can be largely attributed to the empirical and often prolonged use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, lack of antimicrobial stewardship protocols, and suboptimal infection prevention practices. These factors create a selective environment conducive to the proliferation of resistant strains. Our observation that tigecycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (TMP-SMX) retained full sensitivity against all gram-negative isolates is encouraging. These findings support the recommendations made by Soni et al. (2019) and Das et al. (2019),[7,9] who suggested the cautious yet effective use of these agents in MDR scenarios, particularly when other first-line antibiotics fail.

The resistance pattern exhibited by *Staphylococcus aureus* in this study is particularly alarming. The isolate was found to be resistant to vancomycin and teicoplanin, two cornerstone antibiotics in the treatment of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA). Although rare, glycopeptide-resistant MRSA strains have been reported globally and are known to cause treatment failures and elevated mortality in neonates. This resistance pattern not only narrows the treatment options but also indicates the urgent necessity of reinforcing strict infection control measures such as cohort nursing, contact precautions, and routine decolonization where applicable. Our findings align with those of Haider et al. (2018).[8], who emphasized the growing resistance among both Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms in NICUs and recommended the integration of regular antimicrobial resistance surveillance, judicious antibiotic use, and stringent hygiene practices to mitigate the risk.

Overall, the resistance trends highlighted by this study should prompt urgent institutional review of empirical therapy guidelines in NICUs and the establishment of local antibiograms. Continuous training of NICU personnel, adherence to hand

hygiene, and limitation of unnecessary antibiotic exposure are imperative to prevent further escalation of resistance. Future studies incorporating molecular techniques to identify resistance genes and strain typing can offer deeper insights into the transmission dynamics of MDR pathogens within healthcare facilities.

Summary:

Neonatal septicemia is a life-threatening condition affecting newborns within the first 28 days of life, and it continues to be a significant cause of neonatal mortality and morbidity worldwide. This condition is particularly severe in developing and low-resource countries where healthcare access, infection control measures, and diagnostic capabilities are often inadequate. The World Health Organization estimates that infections contribute to nearly 3 million neonatal deaths globally each year, with sepsis playing a central role. In India, the burden of neonatal sepsis is particularly alarming, accounting for 30–50% of all neonatal deaths. Various socio-economic and healthcare-related factors such as limited access to skilled birth attendants, inadequate hygiene, and poor infection control practices contribute to this high mortality.

The study titled “**Prevalence of Bacterial Isolates and Their Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern in Suspected Neonatal Septicemia: A Cross-Sectional Study in Jaipur, India**” addresses this critical issue by examining the bacteriological spectrum and resistance trends among neonates admitted with clinical suspicion of sepsis at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur. The study spanned three months from January to March 2025 and employed a prospective cross-sectional design. Thirty-two neonates with clinical features suggestive of septicemia, such as temperature instability, poor feeding, irritability, and respiratory distress, were included.

Blood samples from these neonates were processed using the BACTEC FX automated culture system. Positive cultures were further analyzed using standard microbiological techniques and confirmed with the VITEK 2 Compact system for both bacterial identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing, in accordance with CLSI guidelines. The antibiotics tested included amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, meropenem, tigecycline, amikacin, and others.

Of the 32 neonates, 8 (25%) yielded positive blood cultures. The gender distribution showed a higher incidence in males (65.6%) compared to females (34.4%). Gram-negative bacilli predominated among the isolates, accounting for 87.5% of the culture-positive cases. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most commonly isolated organism (37.5%), followed by *Pseudomonas spp.* (25%), and one isolate each of *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter spp.*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (12.5% each). These findings are consistent with national and global data indicating a shift from Gram-positive to Gram-negative dominance in NICU-acquired infections.

Antibiotic resistance patterns revealed a disturbing trend. All gram-negative isolates showed complete resistance (100%) to commonly used first-line and even some last-resort antibiotics, including amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, and imipenem. However, they retained 100% sensitivity to tigecycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. Amikacin was effective in 85.7% of the isolates. The lone *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate was resistant to vancomycin and teicoplanin—alarming

findings considering these are essential drugs for treating MRSA infections—but was sensitive to linezolid.

The study also analyzed the association between bacterial species and antibiotic sensitivity. A statistically significant relationship was found between organism type and sensitivity pattern ($p = 0.043$), while resistance patterns across different antibiotics did not show significant variability ($p > 0.05$).

These results underscore the serious issue of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in neonatal units. The emergence and persistence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) organisms in NICUs can be attributed to empirical use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, inadequate infection control, and weak antimicrobial stewardship. The findings echo those of previous Indian studies by Kumar et al. (2024) and Sharma et al. (2022), which reported high levels of resistance among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and other Enterobacteriaceae, particularly to cephalosporins and carbapenems.

Of particular concern in this study is the detection of a vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, indicating the need for enhanced infection control measures, strict hygiene compliance, and isolation practices in NICUs. Studies by Haider et al. (2018) and others have emphasized the rising trend of resistance in both Gram-negative and Gram-positive organisms, suggesting the need for institutional antibiotic policies and continuous surveillance.

Antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) are essential in such settings. These include protocols for antibiotic prescribing, routine audit and feedback, clinician education, and promotion of diagnostic stewardship to avoid overuse or misuse of antibiotics. In addition, non-pharmacological measures like hand hygiene, aseptic techniques, breastfeeding promotion, and minimization of invasive procedures play a crucial role in preventing infections.

The study also highlights the utility of tigecycline and TMP-SMX, which retained full sensitivity against all isolates. These antibiotics, although not typically first-line choices for neonates, could be reconsidered in settings with high MDR prevalence. However, their use should be carefully weighed against toxicity profiles and local clinical guidelines.

In conclusion, the study presents critical data on the local bacterial spectrum and resistance patterns in neonatal septicemia cases in Jaipur. It emphasizes the dominance of MDR Gram-negative bacteria and the growing resistance even among Gram-positive pathogens. The findings support the urgent need for regular antibiogram updates, rational antibiotic use, and stringent infection control practices. These interventions are vital not only for improving neonatal outcomes but also for combating the broader threat of antimicrobial resistance in hospital settings. The study adds valuable insight to regional data, enabling more effective, targeted empirical treatment protocols and encouraging future research into resistance gene profiling and molecular epidemiology of neonatal pathogens.

Conclusion

This study highlights the alarming prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) gram-negative bacilli, particularly *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, as the primary pathogens responsible for neonatal septicemia in the NICU setting of NIMS Hospital, Jaipur. The high resistance rates to commonly used antibiotics, including third-generation cephalosporins and carbapenems, emphasize the urgent need to re-evaluate current empirical treatment protocols. The observed full sensitivity to tigecycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole presents alternative therapeutic options but also calls for cautious and judicious use.

The emergence of vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* further complicates the antimicrobial landscape and underscores the importance of robust infection control strategies. This study reinforces the critical role of continuous microbial surveillance, development of local antibiograms, and implementation of antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) to guide evidence-based treatment decisions.

Ultimately, targeted therapy, strict infection prevention practices, and institutional policies that promote rational antibiotic use are essential to curb the spread of resistance, improve clinical outcomes, and safeguard neonatal health in resource-limited settings.

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In addition to antimicrobial therapy, supportive care including adequate nutrition, maintenance of thermoregulation, oxygen therapy, and monitoring for complications is essential. Infection prevention strategies such as hand hygiene, aseptic techniques, breastfeeding promotion, and minimizing unnecessary invasive procedures are also vital components of neonatal care (Haider et al., 2018).

In the context of Jaipur and the broader Rajasthan region, there is a paucity of updated data regarding the current bacteriological profile and resistance patterns in neonatal septicemia. The present study was undertaken to bridge this knowledge gap and provide valuable insights for clinicians and microbiologists. By identifying the prevalent bacterial pathogens and evaluating their antibiotic sensitivity patterns, this study aims to enhance the effectiveness of empirical therapy and reduce the burden of neonatal sepsis in hospital settings.